

Membrane electrode assembly simulation of anion exchange membrane water electrolysis

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

- A 3D MEA modelling validates AEM with Raney[®]Ni || X37-50 RT || NiFe₂O₄ configuration.
- 3-electrode performance modelled for HER (Raney[®]Ni) and OER (NiFe₂O₄) electrodes.
- 2-phase flow effect on MEA polarization studied and sensitivity analysis performed.
- MEA affected by pH > membrane thickness > temperature > dry cathode feed > flowrate.

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ABSTRACT

Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE) offers a green hydrogen production method that eliminates the need for platinum group metals (PGM) as electrocatalysts. This study employs a COMSOL[®] 6.0 model to simulate a 1x1 cm² Ni fibre – Raney[®] Ni || X37-50RT || NiFe₂O₄ – SS316L fibre AEMWE membrane electrode assembly (MEA). The membrane is set at a thickness of 60 μm, while the anodic and cathodic porous transport layers (PTL) are modelled with a thickness of 370 μm, each having an average porosity of 0.70. The half-cell overpotentials are experimentally measured to validate the half-cell model in a three-electrode setup consisting of (working electrode) || AGAR-Ag/AgCl || Pt-wire (counter electrode). Two freshly prepared MEAs validated the (i) base case and (ii) sensitivity analysis models. The base case model validated the MEA results at 20 °C and 1 atm in 1M KOH electrolyte feed at 1.56 ml min⁻¹ cm⁻². The five parameters studied with the sensitivity analysis revealed the most influential parameters based on area-specific resistance (ASR) change in the following order (+ and – indicate increase and decrease in ASR, respectively): KOH concentration (–97%), membrane thickness (+ 9%), temperature (–4%), cathode feed type (< +0.5%), and KOH flow rate (> –0.5%).

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Nomenclature and Acronyms**Latin Letters**

a	Dimensionless Parameter [-]
A_{cell}	Cell Area [cm ²]
a_i	Reacting Species Activity [-]
b	Dimensionless Parameter [-]
C_D	Drag Coefficient [-]
C_{H_2}	H ₂ Concentration [-]
$C_{H_2}^0$	Equilibrium H ₂ Concentration [-]
C_L	Lift Coefficient [-]
C_O	Instantaneous Oxidising Species Concentration [-]
C_{O_2}	O ₂ Concentration [-]
$C_{O_2}^0$	Equilibrium O ₂ Concentration [-]
$C_{O,ref}$	Oxidising Species Activity at Reference Initial Concentration [-]
C_R	Instantaneous Reducing Species Concentration [-]
$C_{R,ref}$	Reducing Species Activity at Reference Initial Concentration [-]
d_{bubble}	Bubble Diameter [μm]
D_g	Gas Diffusivity [m ² s ⁻¹]
$D_{g,eff}$	Effective Gas Diffusivity [m ² s ⁻¹]
E_a	Anodic Potential [V]
E_c	Cathodic Potential [V]
E_{cell}	Cell Voltage [V]
E_{OCV}	Open Circuit Voltage [V]
E_{rev}^0	Reversible Potential [V]
f_{KOH}	KOH Flow Rate [ml min ⁻¹]
F	Faraday's Constant [96,458 C mol ⁻¹]
$F_{m,i}$	Force Exerted on Phase i by the other Phase [N m ⁻³]
F_i	Volume Forces Exerted on Phase i [N m ⁻³]
j	Current Density [A cm ⁻²]
j_0	Exchange Current Density [A cm ⁻²]
$j_{0,OER}$	Anodic Exchange Current Density [A cm ⁻²]
$j_{0,HER}$	Cathodic Exchange Current Density [A cm ⁻²]
K_d	Gas Dispersion Factor [m s ⁻¹]
m	[mol kg ⁻¹]
M	Molar [mol L ⁻¹]
p	Total pressure [Pa]
$p_{aq,KOH}^{sat}$	Saturated Aqueous KOH Pressure [Pa]
p_{H_2}	Hydrogen Partial Pressure [Pa]
p_{O_2}	Oxygen Partial Pressure [Pa]
p_{H_2O}	Water Vapour Pressure [Pa]
$p_{H_2O}^{sat}$	Saturated Water Vapour Pressure [Pa]
p_{ref}	Reference Pressure [1 atm]
R	Universal Gas Constant [J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
R_a	Anodic Resistance [Ω]
R_c	Cathodic Resistance [Ω]
$R_{contact}$	Contact Resistance [Ω]

R_{ACL}	Anodic Catalyst Layer Surface Roughness [-]
R_{CCL}	Cathodic Catalyst Layer Surface Roughness [-]
R_e	Electric Resistance [Ω]
R_e^a	Anode Electric Resistance [Ω]
R_e^c	Cathode Electric Resistance [Ω]
R_i	Ionic Resistance [Ω]
$R_{i,PTL}$	PTL Ionic Resistance [Ω]
$R_{i,mem}$	Membrane Ionic Resistance [Ω]
T	Temperature [K]
u_i	Phase Velocity [m s ⁻¹]
u_{slip}	Slip Velocity [m s ⁻¹]
V	Cell Voltage [V]
z	Number of Electrons [-]

Greek Letters

α_a	Anodic Charge Transfer Coefficient [-]
α_c	Cathodic Charge Transfer Coefficient [-]
α_v	Active Specific Surface Area [m ⁻¹]
δ_{PTL}	PTL Thickness [μm]
δ_{mem}	Membrane Thickness [μm]
ϵ_{SS316L}	SS316L Fibre Felt Porosity [-]
ϵ_{NiFelt}	Ni Fibre Felt Porosity [-]
η_{act}	Activation Overpotential [V]
η_{act}^a	Anodic Activation Overpotential [V]
η_{act}^c	Cathodic Activation Overpotential [V]
η_{conc}^a	Anodic Concentration Overpotential [V]
η_{conc}^c	Cathodic Concentration Overpotential [V]
η_{conc}	Concentration Overpotentials [V]
η_{ohm}	Ohmic Overpotentials [V]
η_{ref}	Overpotential at the Fixed Reference Initial Concentrations [V]
μ_c	Continuous Phase Viscosity [Pa s]
μ_{mix}	Mixture Viscosity [Pa s]
ν_i	Stoichiometric Coefficient of Reactant i [-]
ν_k	Stoichiometric Coefficient of Product k [-]
ϕ_c	Continuous Phase Volume Fraction [-]
ϕ_d	Dispersed Phase Volume Fraction [-]
$\phi_{d,H_2,max}$	Maximum O ₂ Dispersed Phase Volume Fraction [-]
$\phi_{d,O_2,max}$	Maximum O ₂ Dispersed Phase Volume Fraction [-]
ρ_i	Phase Density [kg m ⁻³]
σ_{KOH}	Aqueous KOH Electrolyte Conductivity [S m ⁻¹]
$\sigma_{KOH,eff}$	Effective aqueous KOH Electrolyte Conductivity [S m ⁻¹]
σ_{mem}	Membrane Conductivity [S m ⁻¹]
$\sigma_{s,SS316L}$	SS316L Fibre Felt Substrate Electrical Conductivity [S m ⁻¹]
$\sigma_{s,NiFelt}$	Ni Fibre Felt Substrate Electrical Conductivity [S m ⁻¹]
τ	Viscous Stress Tensor [Pa]

1. Introduction

The deployment of renewable energy systems has generated tremendous potential for the production of green hydrogen through water

electrolysis. In the low temperature regime (<120 °C) the electrolysis process has been dominated by zero-gap alkaline water electrolyzer (AWE) and proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer (PEMWE) systems. The PEMWE systems can operate with high current densities

Acronyms

AEM	Anion Exchange Membrane
AEMFC	Anion Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells
AEMWE	Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzer
ASR	Area Specific Resistance
AWE	Alkaline Water Electrolyzer
CCS	Catalyst Coated Substrate
CL	Catalyst Layer
DCF	Dry-Cathode Feed
ECSA	Electrochemically Active Surface Area
EPDM	Ethylene Propylene Diene Monomer
GDL	Gas Diffusion Layer
HER	Hydrogen Evolution Reaction
IEC	Ion-Exchange Capacity
KOH	Potassium Hydroxide
MEA	Membrane Electrode Assembly
OER	Oxygen Evolution Reaction
PEMFC	Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell
PEMWE	Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzer
PGM	Platinum Group Metal
PTL	Porous Transport Layer
aPTL	anode Porous Transport Layer
cPTL	cathode Porous Transport Layer
WCF	Wet-Cathode Feed

(>2 A cm⁻²) for less than 2V [1–3], rendering a compact system. The principal disadvantage of the PEMWE is the usage of platinum-group metal (PGM) materials for electrocatalysts and bipolar plates. The usage of non-PGM materials is common in the AWE systems. Although AWE systems use cheaper, relatively less critical materials as electrocatalysts (Ni, Fe, Mo) the current densities are low (≈ 0.5 A cm⁻² at 2V [4,5]. Additionally, AWE exhibit higher gas cross over of H₂ in O₂ due to the usage of porous separator. Anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers (AEMWE) use a polymer electrolyte under alkaline conditions, effectively combining the advantages of the PEMWE and AWE. The performance of AEMWE has been repeatedly reported to reach at least 1 A cm⁻² at 2 V with non-PGM electrocatalysts [6,7].

A standard AEMWE functions with aqueous KOH feed in both electrodes known as wet-cathode feed, as shown in Fig. 1(a). The hydrogen evolution (HER) and the oxygen evolution reactions (OER) occurring at the cathode and the anode respectively are driven by applied electric current (galvanostatic) or voltage difference (potentiostatic). The half-cell reactions are shown in Eqs. (1) and (2) for the cathode and the anode respectively. The electrochemical reactions *pump half – mol* of H₂O to the anode for every *mol* consumed at the cathode. In practice the water transfer through the membrane is higher than the stoichiometric requirements due to high ion exchange capacities (IEC) of the AEM.

The high ion exchange capacity (IEC) results in high water uptake and swelling. The high IEC would also result in higher water transport by diffusion through the membrane, allowing the aqueous KOH to be fed only at the anode, as shown in Fig. 1(b), in a dry cathode feed

configuration. The H₂O required at the cathode is supplied by diffusion from the anode [8].

The performance and degradation analysis studies of AEMWE have picked pace since 2020, with membranes from various manufacturers reaching greater than 1 year (>8700 h) - constant current density performances. The operating conditions of the AEMWE membrane electrode assemblies are critical to maintain durability and potentially manage lifetime [9,10]. Identifying and mapping MEA performances under different temperatures, KOH concentrations and electrolyte feed types (wet or dry cathode feed) helps to characterize MEA requirements to reach such durability. Extensive experiments are necessary to determine the large scale AEMWE implementation feasibility. These *costs of experiments* can be significantly reduced through multiphysics simulation of the MEAs. Additionally, the development of control strategies for AEMWE systems would be beneficial to minimize degradation and improve durability. The interplay of KOH concentration, temperature, pressure and operating current density to meet required hydrogen production is crucial to arrive at an exceptionally low leveled cost of hydrogen. A robust MEA model is a first step towards implementing dynamic control systems, within the validation domain.

The simulation of membrane electrode assembly in anion exchange membrane fuel cells (AEMFC) commonly employs the dusty gas model to describe species transport within gas diffusion electrodes, while the Maxwell–Stefan diffusion model prevails in proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC) systems [11]. Since freezing water in fuel cells is a major concern at low operating temperatures, the emphasis is on examining water distribution, managing water content, and studying species crossover [12]. Hence, precise design of the gas diffusion layer, considering microstructure, porosity, contact angles, and optimal inlet gas humidity, is crucial to manage anode water flooding and cathode water starvation [13,14].

Physicochemical investigation of electrode kinetics using the dusty gas model in one-dimensional planes with spatial averaging is also a predominant technique. The dusty gas model serves as an extension of the Maxwell–Stefan diffusion model for low porosities, which is relevant in the catalyst layers [15–18]. Notably, the Lattice Boltzmann method is utilized to analyse capillary pressure-saturation characteristics in gas diffusion layers (GDLs), specifically to simulate the transport of liquid water [19,20]. However, attention in two-phase flows is directed towards efficiently removing produced water in the absence of bubbles.

In PEMWE, pure deionized water is supplied at the anode (OER electrode), while the unintended crossover of water to the cathode (HER electrode) leads to distinct two-phase behaviour. Understanding the interaction between oxygen bubbles and the porous transport Layer (PTL) is crucial for developing advanced anode microstructures with low concentration overpotentials. The modelling of gas–liquid interfaces predominantly employs mass-momentum conservation equations and Lattice Boltzmann methods [21–24], emphasizing phase separation. The focus is specifically on the transport of specific species, with typically not considering interphase momentum transfers [21,25,26].

Additionally, the PEMWE studies encompass stationary two-phase flows, concentrating on bubble nucleation, growth, coalescence, and detachment without addressing the impact of a continuously increasing bubble fraction as a function of applied current density. Given the significance of only oxygen bubbles in PEMWE, interactions of hydrogen bubbles in the PTLs are not considered when evaluating MEA performance.

Currently, few studies exist on two-phase simulation of AEMWE MEAs. F.M Nafchi et al. numerically modelled a 3D AEMWE with flow channels using Aspen Plus software [27]. The model was validated with experimental data from Li Xiao et al. [28]. The effect of temperature and pressure on AEMWE performance was also studied, showing a better performance at higher temperature and pressure. D. Lee et al. developed an advanced AEMWE CFD-based model [21]. The polarization curve obtained from the model was validated experimentally,

Fig. 1. The anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer in (a) wet cathode feed (standard) operation (b) dry cathode feed operation.

and the species concentrations and pressure drops in the flow channels were simulated. F.M Nafchi et al. [27] and D. Lee [21] models focus extensively on the effect of flow fields on AEMWE performance. Gomez Vidales et al. [22] modelled the influence of operating parameters such as temperature, pressure, KOH concentration, membrane thickness and flow on the AEMWE performance.

However, coupling of MEA performance with two phase fluid characteristics at the MEA and the catalyst coated substrate (CCS) has not been completely investigated. Additionally, while the design of experiments has been implemented to choose the best performing MEA materials [23], there are only a few electrochemical models identifying AEMWE operating profiles for a chosen MEA.

Therefore, in this work, the COMSOL[®] *fuel cell and electrolyzers module* coupled with the *computational fluid dynamics module* are used to validate a standard electrochemical AEMWE cell performance and two-phase behaviour in the porous transport layer (PTL). The activity-based *Butler–Volmer* equation is employed to calculate electrochemical processes, concurrently integrating gas phase production through the *Euler–Euler* equations. The continuity-mass and momentum conservation method for Newtonian fluids, along with the *Navier–Stokes* equations are used to calculate the velocity and the viscosity profiles in a finite mesh volume. The local change in viscosity is adapted based on the Krieger viscosity model. Further, *inter-phase momentum transfer* is calculated based on bubble phase lift, drag and dispersion forces to evaluate instantaneous gas fraction. The *Schiller–Naumann* drag model is used to describe inter-phase drag coefficients. The technique is applied to both the HER and OER electrodes in the standard wet cathode feed configuration (WCF).

The numerical model is first validated with three-electrode measurements separately for the CCS: anode PTL (aPTL) and cathode PTL (cPTL), following the good practices for electrolysis cells [24]. The validated half-cell model is extended to map the MEA performance using commercial materials ensuring reproducibility. Two MEAs are utilized to validate (i) the base case model and (ii) the sensitivity analysis model ensuring robustness. Further, a ranking table is developed based on area specific resistance (ASR) change, to summarize the effect of sensitivity parameters, such as, KOH supporting electrolyte concentration, membrane thickness, temperature, supporting electrolyte feed type and flowrate.

2. Model description

The AEMWE model was developed considering realistic cross sectional dimensions of commercial PTL. A representative 3D domain of $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ was chosen to reduce computational costs. The model domain includes PTL for HER, an AEM and a PTL for OER. All the associated values of measurements were normalized as a function of area.

The existing literature and models on AEMWE performance simulation were analysed and adapted, as represented in Fig. 2. The model was progressively developed as 1D, 2D and 3D geometries. Further, the model is validated and tuned with series of experimental measurements under various conditions. The *model description* section is divided into the following subsections:

- Section 2.1: *Governing Equations* - describes the governing (electrochemical and two-phase flow) equations that contribute to the model physics.
- Section 2.2: *Numerical Model* - describes the numerical model built in terms of cell structure, components, major assumptions taken and how it was constructed in COMSOL[®] 6.0 (domain and boundary conditions).
- Section 2.3: *Experimental Setup* - describes the experimental setup and conditions used for operating three-electrode and the MEA.

2.1. Governing equations

The AEMWE model is governed by a combination of two sets of equations: electrochemical and fluid flow equations. The electrochemical equations determine the cell voltage, the activation overpotentials of HER and OER, in addition to the ohmic losses in the MEA. Meanwhile, the two-phase fluid flow equations determine the effect of bubble formation on the cell performance, and model the two-phase behaviour in the PTL.

2.1.1. Electrochemical equations

The most general electrochemical governing equation that determines the different contributing factors to the cell voltage (E_{cell}) is shown in Eq. (4) [25],

$$E_{cell} = E_{OCV} + \eta_{act} + \eta_{conc} + \eta_{ohm} \quad (4)$$

where η_{act} , η_{conc} and η_{ohm} are the activation, concentration and ohmic overpotentials (V) respectively.

2.1.1.1. *The open circuit voltage (E_{OCV})*. A water electrolyzer system undergoing hydrogen and oxygen evolution reactions is governed by the Nernst equation (5), which depends on the temperature T and the activity of the reacting species a_i .

$$E_{OCV} = E_{rev}^0(T) - \frac{RT}{zF} \ln \left(\frac{\prod_i a_i^{v_i}}{\prod_k a_k^{v_k}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $E_{rev}^0(T)$ is the reversible cell voltage (V), R is the ideal gas constant ($8.3145 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), F is Faraday's constant ($96,485.332 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$), z is the number of participating electrons ($z = 2$ for AEMWE), v_i and v_k are the stoichiometric coefficients of reactants and products, respectively. The reversible cell voltage (E_{rev}^0) is temperature dependent and is written in Eq. (6) [26], assuming no gas crossover.

$$E_{rev}^0(T) = 1.481 - 0.000846T \quad (6)$$

For the water splitting reaction of Eq. (3), the OCV can be defined with anode and cathode activities as shown in Eq. (7).

$$E_{OCV} = E_{rev}^0(T) - \frac{RT}{zF} \ln \left(\frac{a_{H_2} a_{O_2}^{1/2}}{a_{H_2O}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The behaviour of a species activity governed by the ideal gas law can be characterized by the ratio of partial pressures to a standard reference pressure. Further, the AEMWE water species activity can be

Fig. 2. Flowchart detailing the structure of the model validation.

calculated as a ratio of saturated water vapour pressure in contact with the electrolyte and the saturated vapour pressure in pure water [29]. Therefore, the open circuit voltage (E_{OCV}) can be adapted as a ratio of partial pressures, as shown in Eq. (8) [26],

$$E_{OCV} = E_{rev}^0(T) - \frac{RT}{zF} \ln \left(\frac{p_{H_2} p_{O_2}^{1/2}}{p_{H_2O}} \right) \quad (8)$$

where, p_{H_2} , p_{O_2} and p_{H_2O} are the partial pressures of hydrogen, oxygen and water vapour pressure, respectively.

The partial pressure terms of Eq. (8) are obtained from pressure balance for each half-cell. At the anode, the pressure balance is given as in Eq. (9),

$$p_{O_2} = \frac{p - p_{H_2O}^{sat}}{p_{ref}} \quad (9)$$

where p is the total pressure of the system and $p_{ref} = 1$ atm is the reference pressure.

At the cathode, the pressure balance is given as in Eq. (10),

$$p_{H_2} = \frac{p - p_{H_2O}^{sat}}{p_{ref}} \quad (10)$$

The saturated water vapour pressure is defined by the Buck's equation (11) [30].

$$p_{H_2O}^{sat} = 0.6112 \cdot \exp \left(18.678 - \frac{T}{234.5} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{T}{257.15 + T} \right) \quad (11)$$

where $p_{H_2O}^{sat}$ is in kPa and T is °C.

Further, the partial water vapour pressure is defined, as shown in Eq. (12). The $p_{H_2O}^{sat}$ must be converted to bar before using Eq. (12).

$$p_{H_2O} = \frac{p_{aq,KOH}^{sat}}{p_{H_2O}^{sat}} \quad (12)$$

where, p_{H_2O} is the partial water vapour pressure and $p_{aq,KOH}^{sat}$ is the aqueous potassium hydroxide saturated vapour pressure at the respective electrodes and can be calculated using Eq. (13) [31].

$$p_{aq,KOH}^{sat} = 10^a \cdot p_{H_2O}^{sat} \cdot (T)^b \quad (13)$$

The parameters a and b depend on the molality (m) of aq.KOH systems, as shown in Eq. (14).

$$\begin{aligned} a &= -0.01508 m - 1.6788 \times 10^{-3} m^2 + 2.25887 \times 10^{-5} m^3 \\ b &= 1 - 1.2062 \times 10^{-3} m + 5.6024 \times 10^{-4} m^2 - 7.8228 \times 10^{-6} m^3 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

2.1.1.2. Activation overpotential. The general form of the Butler–Volmer equation sufficiently describes the electrode kinetics, as shown in Eq. (15),

$$j = j_0 \left[\exp \left(\frac{\alpha_a z F \eta_{act}^a}{RT} \right) - \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_c z F \eta_{act}^c}{RT} \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

where η_{act}^a and η_{act}^c (V) are the anodic and cathodic activation overpotentials, respectively; α_a and α_c are the anodic and cathodic charge transfer coefficients. The operating current density is represented by j ($A m^{-2}$), while the exchange current density is given by j_0 ($A m^{-2}$).

Assuming a symmetric reaction ($\alpha_a = \alpha_c$) [32], the anodic and cathodic activation overpotentials are obtained from Eqs. (16) and (17), respectively [32–34],

$$\eta_{act}^a = \frac{RT}{\alpha_a F} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{j}{2R_{ACL} \cdot j_{0,OER}} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\eta_{act}^c = \frac{RT}{\alpha_c F} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{j}{2R_{CCL} \cdot j_{0,HER}} \right) \quad (17)$$

where the anodic and cathodic exchange current densities are represented by $j_{0,OER}$ and $j_{0,HER}$ ($A m^{-2}$), respectively. The surface roughness of the anodic and the cathodic catalyst layers are represented by R_{ACL} (-) and R_{CCL} (-), respectively. As the general Butler–Volmer equation does not accurately consider the local concentration changes, the adapted form is used to further describe the local electrode kinetics, as shown in Eq. (18) [35].

$$j = j_{o,ref} \left(\frac{C_R}{C_{R,ref}} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_a F \eta_{ref}}{RT} \right) - \left(\frac{C_O}{C_{O,ref}} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{\alpha_c F \eta_{ref}}{RT} \right) \quad (18)$$

where $C_{R,ref}$ and $C_{O,ref}$ are the reducing and oxidizing species activities at reference initial concentrations, respectively; η_{ref} is the overpotential at the fixed reference initial concentrations; C_R and C_O are the instantaneous reducing and oxidizing species redox couple concentration. The exchange current density under reference conditions is defined by Eq. (19).

$$j_{o,ref} = j_{0,O} \cdot C_{O,ref}^{\frac{\alpha_a}{z}} \cdot C_{R,ref}^{\frac{\alpha_c}{z}} \quad (19)$$

where, $j_{0,O}$ is the exchange current density under standard conditions. The reference conditions are state dependent (initial conditions), while the standard conditions are fixed at 25 °C and 1 atm pressure.

2.1.1.3. Concentration overpotential. Mass transport resistance due to produced gas accumulation in the catalyst (CL) and PTL, increases cell voltage [36], this overpotential is known as the concentration overpotential, and can be described in Eqs. (20) and (21) for the anode and the cathode respectively,

$$\eta_{conc}^a = \frac{RT}{4F} \ln \left(\frac{C_{O_2}}{C_{O_2}^0} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$\eta_{conc}^c = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{C_{H_2}}{C_{H_2}^0} \right) \quad (21)$$

where C_{O_2} and C_{H_2} are the O_2 and H_2 concentrations and $C_{O_2}^0$ $C_{H_2}^0$ are the standard O_2 and H_2 concentrations.

2.1.1.4. Ohmic overpotential. The ohmic overpotential (η_{ohm}), directly proportional to the applied current, is the sum (serial disposition) of the electric and ionic resistances in the cell [32], and can be expressed as in Eq. (22),

$$\eta_{ohm} = j A_{cell} (R_e + R_i) \quad (22)$$

where A_{cell} is the cell area (in m^2), R_e is the electric and R_i is the ionic resistance (both in Ω) The electric resistance is due to anodic and cathodic CL and PTL resistance and the interfacial contact resistances (mainly between CLs and membrane), [34] which results in Eq. (23).

$$R_e = R_e^a + R_e^c + R_{contact} \quad (23)$$

The ionic resistance (R_i) contribution is dominant across the membrane (OH^- for AEMWE), and in the PTL. The aPTL and cPTL contribute to the ionic resistance due to ion transfer from the membrane to the reaction sites. The aPTL, membrane and cPTL resistances are in series and can be written as shown in Eq. (24).

$$R_i = R_{i,aPTL} + R_{i,mem} + R_{i,cPTL} \quad (24)$$

Further, the anodic ($R_{i,aPTL}$) and the cathodic ($R_{i,cPTL}$) PTL ionic resistances, are written in Eq. (25),

$$R_{i,PTL} = \frac{\delta_{PTL}}{\sigma_{KOH} \cdot \phi_c \cdot A_{cell}} \quad (25)$$

where δ_{PTL} is the PTL thickness (m), σ_{KOH} is the KOH electrolyte conductivity ($S m^{-1}$), and ϕ_c is the KOH volume fraction in the PTL (dimensionless).

Additionally, the membrane ionic resistance ($R_{i,mem}$) is the given by Eq. (26),

$$R_{i,mem} = \frac{\delta_{mem}}{\sigma_{mem} \cdot A_{cell}} \quad (26)$$

where δ_{mem} is the membrane thickness (m), σ_{mem} is the membrane conductivity ($S m^{-1}$), and A_{cell} is the cell area (m^2). The equations for the membrane (σ_{mem}) and KOH electrolyte (σ_{KOH}) conductivities were extracted from [37,38] respectively, and then implemented in the model. Additionally, the gas evolution during the electrolysis process occupies the liquid supporting electrolyte volume effectively reducing the conductivity of the aq. KOH used. The change in the supporting electrolyte conductivity follows Bruggemann's effective medium approximation as shown in Eq. (27).

$$\sigma_{KOH,eff} = \phi_c^{\frac{3}{2}} \sigma_{KOH} \quad (27)$$

2.1.2. Two-phase flow equations

An Euler–Euler model was used to study the two-phase fluid flow inside the cell PTL. The Euler–Euler model is chosen as it considers the interaction between the gas bubbles (dispersed phase) and the liquid electrolyte (continuous phase). The Euler–Euler model averages the Navier–Stokes equations for each of the continuous and dispersed phases over a volume that is considered relatively small to the total geometry and large compared to the dispersed phase. The continuous and dispersed phases are also considered to be interpenetrating.

2.1.2.1. Continuity - mass balance. The mass balance inside the PTL for each phase is described by the continuity Eq. (28),

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_i \phi_i) + \nabla \cdot (\rho_i \phi_i \mathbf{u}_i) = 0 \quad (28)$$

where ρ_i the phase density ($kg m^{-3}$), ϕ_i is the volume fractions of phase i ($i = c$ for continuous phase; $i = d$ for dispersed phase), and \mathbf{u}_i the phase velocity ($m s^{-1}$). Eq. (28) is valid for both the continuous and dispersed phase, assuming no mass transfer occurs between the phases [39]. In the PTL, the gas and liquid phases are considered complementary, occupying the total void volume, as detailed in Eq. (29).

$$\phi_c + \phi_d = 1 \quad (29)$$

Assuming incompressible fluids, Eq. (28) can be simplified into Eq. (30).

$$\frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\phi_i \mathbf{u}_i) = 0 \quad (30)$$

Further simplification of Eq. (30), results in the modified continuity equation as shown in Eq. (31).

$$\nabla \cdot (\phi_d \mathbf{u}_d + \mathbf{u}_c (1 - \phi_d)) = 0 \quad (31)$$

The simplified continuity Eq. (31) is used to determine the phase distributions across the model domain, explained further in Section 2.2.

2.1.2.2. Momentum balance. Assuming no surface tension, and uniform bubble size distribution for the gas bubbles, the momentum balance equations in the Euler–Euler model are written in Eq. (32) for each phase i (c or d) [39].

$$\rho_i \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_i \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_i \right] = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_i + \rho_i \mathbf{g} + \frac{\mathbf{F}_{m,i}}{\phi_i} + \mathbf{F}_i \quad (32)$$

where the pressure of the mixture is given by p (Pa), assuming both phases are at the same pressure, \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity ($\approx 9.81 m s^{-2}$) and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ the viscous stress tensor for each phase (Pa). The force exerted on phase i by the other phase is noted as $\mathbf{F}_{m,i}$ ($N m^{-3}$). All the other volume forces exerted of phase i are noted as \mathbf{F}_i ($N m^{-3}$).

Assuming Newtonian fluids, the viscous stress tensor ($\boldsymbol{\tau}_i$) for phase i can be described by Eq. (33) [39].

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_i = \mu_{mix} (\nabla \mathbf{u}_i + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_i)^T) - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_i) \mathbf{I} \quad (33)$$

where μ_{mix} is the dynamic viscosity of the mixture (Pa s) and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix.

Momentum balance equations are used to compute the velocities of each phase to understand the dynamics and behaviour of the fluids in the cell.

2.1.2.3. Viscosity model. The mixture viscosity used in the model is given by the Krieger viscosity model [40] described in Eq. (34),

$$\mu_{mix} = \mu_c \left(1 - \frac{\phi_d}{\phi_{d,max}}\right)^{-2.5\phi_{d,max}} \quad (34)$$

where $\phi_{d,max}$ is the maximum packing limit, equal to 1 in the case of gas bubbles in the liquid. The Krieger viscosity model integrates the dispersed and continuous phase viscosity based on the dispersed phase fraction (ϕ_d), to determine the mixer viscosity. Further details related to the fluid flow equations as well as the molar cell flows are elaborated in the supplementary information S1.

2.1.2.4. Interphase momentum transfer. The forces exerted by one phase on the other ($\mathbf{F}_{m,i}$) represent the interphase momentum transfer, which identifies and computes the interaction between the two phases. In the case of gas bubbles dispersed in liquid, lift, drag and bubble dispersion forces are present [41], as represented in Eq. (35).

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \underbrace{-\frac{3}{4}\phi_d\rho\frac{C_D}{d_{bubble}}|\mathbf{u}_{slip}|\mathbf{u}_{slip}}_{\text{Drag Force}} - \underbrace{\phi_d\rho C_L|\mathbf{u}_{slip}|\nabla\times\mathbf{u}_c}_{\text{Lift Force}} - \underbrace{\phi_d\rho\frac{K_d}{d_{bubble}}|\mathbf{u}_{slip}|\nabla\phi_d}_{\text{Bubble Dispersion Force}} \quad (35)$$

The first term in Eq. (35) is the drag force, the second term is the lift force and the third term is the bubble dispersion force; where \mathbf{F}_i is the vector of the volume forces applied to phase i ; C_D is the drag coefficient; C_L the lift coefficient; d_{bubble} (m) is the average bubble diameter; \mathbf{u}_{slip} (m s^{-1}) the slip velocity; \mathbf{u}_c (m s^{-1}) the continuous phase velocity; ρ (kg m^{-3}) the mixture density and K_d (m s^{-1}) the gas dispersion factor [41].

The slip velocity is the relative velocity between the dispersed and the continuous phase [41] written in Eq. (36).

$$\mathbf{u}_{slip} = \mathbf{u}_d - \mathbf{u}_c \quad (36)$$

The Schiller–Naumann [42] drag model is used to describe the drag forces exerted on each phase, and the drag coefficient is therefore written in Eq. (37).

$$C_D = \begin{cases} \frac{24}{Re}(1 + 0.15Re^{0.687}) & Re < 1000 \\ 0.44 & Re > 1000 \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

Since KOH electrolyte is introduced in low velocities in the cell, the flow is laminar and the Reynolds number is less than 100, as calculated from based on the operating conditions [43]. Therefore, the first case for the drag coefficient is chosen.

2.2. Numerical model

The model is first solved by using a *stationary study* following the Butler–Volmer equation rendering electrochemical information. Then, *Euler–Euler model*, *laminar flow physics interface* is added to the model and coupled with *hydroxide (OH⁻) exchange water electrolyzer physics*. The *stationary study* does not consider the bubble generation effects and is used as an initialization to the *time-dependent study*. The *time-dependent study* simulates the two-phase behaviour in the AEMWE and the effect of bubble formation on cell performance. The generated data is post-processed in MATLAB and a sensitivity analysis of the parameters is performed.

Table 1

Structural parameters and components of 3D-MEA model.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Cell area	A_{cell}	1×1 [cm^2]
Membrane material	–	Sustainion® X37-50RT
Membrane thickness	δ_{mem}	60 [μm]
Anodic substrate material	–	SS316L
Anodic electrocatalyst	–	NiFe ₂ O ₄
Anodic PTL thickness	δ_{aPTL}	370 [μm]
Anodic PTL porosity	ϵ_{SS316L}	0.70
Cathodic substrate material	–	Ni fibre felt
Cathodic PTL thickness	δ_{cPTL}	370 [μm]
Cathodic electrocatalyst	–	Raney® Ni
Cathodic PTL porosity	ϵ_{NiFelt}	0.70

Table 2

Operating conditions for 3D-MEA model - base case.

Parameter	Symbol	Value/State
Temperature	T	20 [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
KOH concentration	c_{KOH}	1 [M]
Pressure	p	1 [atm]
Total flow rate	f_{tot}	1.56 [$\text{ml min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$]
Electrolyte feed type	–	Wet cathode
Electric conductivity of cPTL	$\sigma_{s,NiFelt}$	$\approx 5.36 \times 10^6$ [S m^{-1}]
Electric conductivity of aPTL	$\sigma_{s,SS316L}$	$\approx 1.72 \times 10^5$ [S m^{-1}]

2.2.1. Cell structure and components

A 3D MEA-mesh is constructed based on the operating principle of the AEMWE as shown in Fig. 3(a). The aq.KOH electrolyte enters along the y -axis. The cell is composed of three layers: a Sustainion® X37-50 RT - Teflon reinforced 60 μm thick anion-exchange membrane (AEM), surrounded by aPTL and cPTL.

Porous substrates are used as PTL, with SS316L fibre felt being the anodic substrate and Ni fibre felt as the cathodic substrate. Both the aPTL and cPTL had a porosity of 0.70 as specified by the manufacturer. The anodic and cathodic electrocatalysts used are NiFe₂O₄ and Raney® Ni, respectively. The MEA details have been summarized in Table 1. Both the anodic and cathodic catalyst layers (CLs) are located at the PTL-membrane interface and are considered to be infinitely thin.

2.2.2. Operating conditions and assumptions

A base case representing the experimental operating conditions is built for the model to validate the experimental results. In the base case, the cell is operating at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 1 M KOH electrolyte, at atmospheric pressure (Table 2). The 1 M KOH electrolyte is introduced from the bottom of the cell in the y -axis direction Fig. 3(a), equally into both anodic and cathodic PTL (wet-cathode feed type), with a $f_{\text{KOH}} = 1.56 \text{ ml min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ total flow rate. Substrate electrical conductivity are assumed to be isotropic and independent of temperature, with values fixed at room temperature ($\sigma_{s,NiFelt} \approx 5.36 \times 10^6$ and $\sigma_{s,SS316L} \approx 1.72 \times 10^5$ (S m^{-1})).

2.2.3. Mesh and boundary conditions

A coarse physics-controlled mesh is automatically generated by COMSOL® 6.0, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The distribution of the mesh is concentrated at the boundaries and at the inter-layers. The choice of the physics-controlled mesh is justified due to higher accuracy than the user-defined mesh. The mesh size, corner refinement and boundary layers are automatically adapted based on chosen physics interface settings. In this case two-physics i.e the electrochemical (Butler–Volmer kinetics) and the fluid dynamics (Euler–Euler model) are coupled together and computed in the mesh domain. The corner refinement node creates a smoothed edge at borders of the geometry, preventing convergence anomaly. Moreover, the use of a coarse mesh is made as it reduces computation time, without affecting the accuracy of the model. The boundary layers, membrane-PTL interface and the membrane mesh elements are represented in the 2D cross section of Fig. 3(a).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3. (a) (From left to right) The 3D MEA used in the model, 3D coarse mesh and the 2D schematic representing the modelling domain of the MEA in yz plane (figure not to scale). (b) The three-electrode setup (WE||AGAR||PtWire) used to measure the substrate overpotentials (adopted from [44]). (c) The experimental setup schematic used to perform MEA polarization measurements.

An interplay of the flux based and constraint based boundary conditions define the initialization state of the model. The supporting electrolyte flowrate and applied current density are defined as *flux controlled boundaries* (also known as Neumann boundary). As the model developed is a *well-posed* problem every flux condition results in a unique values of dependant variable, chiefly the MEA voltage. As the flowrate and applied current density are known flux quantity the model computes the dependant variables such as the MEA voltage and gas fractions. The inlet boundary for the KOH is set at the bottom of the geometry (along y axis), opposite to gravity suggesting vertical MEA orientation. The cathode (HER) outer wall boundary is grounded (negative electrode) while the current density is applied at the anode

(OER) outer wall boundary (positive electrode). Further, the following assumptions are made

- (i). The continuous and dispersed phases have the same velocity at time $t = 0$ s, equal to the aqueous KOH flowrate.
- (ii). No-slip conditions at the outer boundaries.
- (iii). Zero gauge pressure at the MEA outlet with no viscous stress.
- (iv). Continuous phase: inward OH^- flux at the membrane — PTL interface
- (v). Dispersed phase: outward gas flux at the membrane — PTL interface.

- (vi). Homogeneous temperature, pressure, electric, ionic conductivity, KOH electrolyte concentration, and applied current density distribution throughout the simulation run time.

2.3. Experimental setup

2.3.1. Three electrode setup

The performance of cPTL and aPTL is analysed using a three electrode setup, as shown in Fig. 3(b). The 3 electrode setup consisted of working electrode || AGAR-Ag/AgCl || Pt-wire (counter electrode). The corresponding electrodes were tested for overpotentials using the methodology mentioned in our previous study [44]. The OER linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) scan range was between +0.3 V and +0.9 V E_{an} versus RHE, while the HER LSV scan range was between -0.3 V and -1.10 E_{cat} versus RHE in 1M KOH. The scan rate was set to 1 mV s^{-1} .

2.3.2. MEA testing setup

Two MEAs with Ni Fibre - Raney® Ni || X37-50RT || NiFe₂O₄ - SS316L Fibre were tested, first to validate the model and second to perform the sensitivity analysis. EPDM gaskets were used as MEA seals with an average clamping pressure of 59 N cm^{-2} . Argon gas was bubbled through the liquid media to avoid atmospheric CO₂ dissolution, as shown in schematic Fig. 3(c). Since argon is 38% heavier than air, a gaseous layer isolates the KOH solution and atmospheric CO₂. The current density - voltage (jV) scans were performed between 1.2 to 2.5 V at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} . A higher scan rate compared to the three electrode measurements were chosen to offset the effects of Joule heating. The results from the three electrode and the MEA tests were combined to validate the built electrochemical model.

3. Results and discussion

The section is divided into the following subsections:

- Section 3.1: *Base Case Model Validation* - initial experimental operating conditions-based model to validate the experimental results.
- Section 3.2: *Sensitivity Analysis* - identifies the most important operating parameters that contribute to the cell performance.
- Section 3.3: *MEA Performance Ranking Table* - Ranks the parameters simulated in Section 3.2 by their contribution to the cell performance.

3.1. Base case model validation

The model overpotentials were validated through the three electrode measurements as shown in Fig. 4(a). The electrochemical active surface area was calculated using the double-layer capacitance method, as described in sup. section S2.1 and figure S2 (a and b). The scan rates used were between 1 to 9 mV s^{-1} in a potential range of ± 50 mV for both HER and OER electrocatalysts. The HER and OER electrodes had similar ECSA ≈ 51 cm^2 , as seen in sup. figure S2 (c). The ECSA were used to calculate the standard reference exchange current densities, as described in sup. equation S10, listed in table S2.

The anode electrocatalyst NiFe₂O₄ had a better performance than the cathode Raney® - Ni. While three electrode measurements of Raney®-Ni has shown very good HER electrocatalyst under traditional alkaline (30 wt% KOH) conditions; @25 °C, $\eta_{(HER)} = 300$ mV, $j = 2$ A cm^{-2} [45], the performance remains poor in AEMWE conditions (~ 4 wt% KOH) [46,47], potentially reaching 1 A cm^{-2} between $\eta_{(HER)} = 400$ to 500 mV. The anode electrocatalyst NiFe₂O₄ has a low onset potential and high activity. The spinel is being established as the most promising OER electrocatalyst under AEMWE conditions [46].

Further, the 3-electrode model was adapted for MEA performance analysis. The adapted model closely matches the experimental data as shown in Fig. 4(b). Three points of interest were analysed, the 0.5 A

Table 3

The cell voltage and H₂ and O₂ gas fractions at the applied current densities of base case model.

Applied current density (A cm^{-2})	Cell voltage		Max. gas fractions	
	(V_{Exp})	(V_{model})	($\phi_{d,H_2,max}$)	($\phi_{d,O_2,max}$)
0.5	2.03	2.04	8%	4%
1	2.22	2.21	$\sim 17\%$	8%
1.2	2.29	2.27	$\sim 21\%$	10%

cm^{-2} , which marks the beginning of bubble formation [48], the 1 A cm^{-2} , an objective current density to be reached, and 1.2 A cm^{-2} , which marks the end of the experimental base case applied current density sweep. Only minor differences (up to 20 mV) at the end of the sweep are observed due to mass transfer limitations of the experimental setup.

The volume fractions of the produced H₂ and O₂ gases in the PTL are highest at the outlet of the cell (top) as shown in represented in Fig. 4(c). Higher bubble concentrations are observed at the interface between the membrane and the PTL, as this is the region of gas production (infinitely thin catalyst layers). A lower gas volume fraction is recorded at the outer edges of the cell as they are the farthest from the catalyst layers. It can be also observed that the gas fraction of produced hydrogen is approximately double that of the produced oxygen, indicating the preservation of the stoichiometric ratio of 2:1 between H₂ and O₂. The resulting gas fractions under varying current densities has been summarized in Table 3. These findings therefore illustrate the behaviour of bubbles within the PTL.

The model fit control strategy uses the ECSA and exchange current densities, calculated using the three-electrode measurements, to isolate the local current densities. However, the double-layer capacitance route of calculating ECSA is relevant only at *mass transfer limitation free* conditions. Although the values are normalized spatially, extrapolating the available performance trends to stack relevant sizes, for example, 100 cm^2 , could result in multiple combinations of local currents, yielding the same J-V curve.

Modelling and evaluating a segmented electrode or membrane electrode assemblies would then be required to predict the MEA performance accurately. Such a methodology has already been implemented in high-temperature solid oxide electrochemical cells [49,50] for performance as well as degradation studies [51]. Recently, Indro Biswas et al. [52] showed that water starvation, thermal gradients, and local current distributions affect the segmented PEM and AEM water electrolyzer technologies. Furthermore, the evolution of bubbles at the electrode-electrolyte interface, contributing to overpotentials could be engineered using segmented electrodes [53], rendering insights bubble nucleation, growth, coalescence and detachment processes.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis

A freshly prepared MEA with similar composition as the validated MEA was assembled for sensitivity analysis of KOH concentration and temperature. The KOH concentration was varied from lower concentration, 0.01 M (pH 12), 0.1 M (pH 13) and 1 M (pH 14), to limit exposure to excess KOH. At each concentration, current density-voltage scans were performed between 1.2 V to 2.5 V at varying temperatures. The chosen temperatures were 30, 50, 60, and 80 °C, based on operating points studied in literature [54-57]. The developed model was also used to validate the cell performance for the varying parameters, and was further used to predict the performance of the MEA under changing membrane thickness, flow rates and cathode feed (dry vs. wet cathode feed).

Fig. 4. (a) Base case 3-electrode model validation at 20 °C, 1 M KOH, 1 atm. (b) Base case 3D MEA model validation (20 °C, 1 M KOH, 1 atm electrolyte introduced at 1,56 ml min⁻¹ wet-cathode feed) (c) HER and OER produced gas volume fractions (ϕ_d) at 0.5 A cm⁻², 1 A cm⁻² and 1.21 A cm⁻².

3.2.1. KOH concentration

The effect of KOH concentration on the MEA was studied at a nominal temperature of 60 °C. The MEA barely performs at pH 12 (63 mA cm⁻² at 2.5 V), as shown in Fig. 5(a). The MEA reaches a current density of 0.52 A cm⁻² at 2.5 V at pH 13, while reaching 1.41 A cm⁻² at pH 14 implying significant performance improvements. The corresponding area specific resistance (ASR) drop by 96% between pH 12 to 14 at 2.5 V, is shown in Fig. 5(b). The gas fractions (ϕ_d) at 2.5 V increase between pH 12 to pH 14 due to increase in current density, as shown in Fig. 5(c). The fractions maintain the stoichiometry of 2:1 between HER and OER, following the water splitting reactions. A decaying concentration gradient is observed from the membrane surface towards the PTL wall, suggesting larger amount of generation at the membrane catalyst interface. A concentration gradient can also be observed along the flow direction, portraying electrolyte replacement by H₂ and O₂.

The lower KOH concentration increases the OER overpotentials and the membrane ohmic resistivity. The OER overpotential increases due to scarcity of OH⁻ ions [58,59]. Additionally, lower KOH concentrations result in larger OER bubble size (> 30 μm) which could potentially block liquid electrolyte transport to the active sites in the GDE [60,61]. The ionic conductivity in the membrane largely depends on ion concentration, mesoscale ion transport pathways (tortuosity) and nanoscale electrostatic interactions (OH⁻ ion solvation energies) [62,63]. Further, the supporting electrolyte improves the conductivity of X37-50RT membranes between 20 to 40 mS cm⁻¹ for a pH range of 12-14 [64]. Effectively, the lower OH⁻ concentrations reduce the membrane conductivity which results in irreversible backbone polymer degradation of the AEM [65].

The modelled MEA has a good match with the experimental data, achieved by temperature compensating the exchange current densities [66]. The membrane conductivity was compensated as function of pH largely due to the properties of the X37-50RT [10]. There is a possibility of creation of a Donnan exclusion zone [67] at concentrations greater than 0.1M KOH with X37 membranes [64,68], resulting in improvement of performance by a factor of 10, between pH 12 (0.01 M) to 13 (0.1 M).

3.2.2. Temperature

The temperature largely effects the membrane ohmic resistance, followed by the kinetic overpotentials. Higher temperature results in higher exchange current densities, i.e., faster reaction; higher ion mobility, and higher membrane and electrolyte conductivity. The experimental j-V data was fit with the model for pH14 as shown in Fig. 6(a). The experiment revealed a plateau in performance improvement between 60 to 80 °C, suggesting the operating temperature of 60 °C being sufficient to operate at current density of 1 A cm⁻². Similar trends were observed with the experimental data for pH 12 and 13 as shown in sup. figure (S3 (i) and (ii)). The model was extended to pH12 and 13 to reveal the extent of temperature sensitivity as a function of pH, shown in Fig. 6(b). The temperature sensitivity has a larger effect with increasing electrolyte concentration; resulting in pH14 having the highest increase in current density (~ 450 mA cm⁻² at 2.5 V).

The activation of the MEA can be observed through the reduction in ASR between 30 °C and 50 °C for pH 14 as shown in Fig. 6(c). Similar trends have been observed for pH 12 and 13, shown in sup. figure(S3(iii) and (iv)) respectively. The increase in ASR is 2.5 times between pH14 and 13, while nearly 32 times between pH14 and 12 as indicated in Fig. 6(d).

Fig. 5. The effect of pH/KOH concentration on cell performance at 1 atm, 60 °C with 1.56 ml min^{-1} wet-cathode feed observed in: (a) polarization plots (b) current density and area specific resistance (ASR) values obtained at 2.5 V (c) HER and OER gas fractions at 2.5 V (front plane).

Table 4

The maximum H_2 gas fraction (%) in the PTL as a function of pH, temperature and current density.

Max. gas fraction ($\phi_{d,H_2,max} - \%$)	Current density ($A \cdot cm^{-2}$)	Temperature (°C)				
		30	50	60	80	
pH	12	0.03	0.25	0.27	0.30	0.38
	13	0.29	7.35	5.12	4.54	5.33
	14	1	12.64	8.68	7.38	9.33

Temperature also has a significant effect on bubble dispersion in the electrolyte media. The bubbles generated diffuses away from the membrane and into the PTL with increasing temperature as shown in Fig. 6(e). The detachment trend is independent of the electrolyte pH and current densities. The nominal current density of 1 A cm^{-2} was chosen for pH 14, while maximum current densities of 0.29 and 0.03 A cm^{-2} at 2.5 V, 30 °C were fixed for pH13 and 12 respectively. The diffusion coefficient for O_2 and H_2 in aqueous solutions increase with increasing temperature, while the supporting electrolyte viscosity decreases [69]. The *diffusion increase- viscosity reduction* combination results in improved bubble evacuation effectively reducing mass transfer limitations. The bubble dispersion away from the catalyst layer is critical to sustain the electrolysis operations at high current densities as more ECSA is made available and is summarized in Table 4.

The effect of temperature on bubble formation is observed for PEMWE in [48], where the oxygen bubble diameter increased by 112% and the number of oxygen bubbles by 117% when increasing the temperature from 40 °C to 80 °C. These results show the influence of temperature on the oxygen bubbles in size and number. They also show the effect of temperature on the bubble formation and growth

rate [48], as temperature facilitates bubble coalescence. It was shown that the rate of bubble growth increases by 3% for every 10 K increase in temperature [48]. The temperature also has influence on all the cell performance contributing factors such as the open circuit voltage and activation, ohmic and diffusion overpotentials [48].

3.2.3. Membrane thickness

The membrane thickness has predominant effects on AEM performance. Thinner membranes have low ohmic resistance due to smaller ionic travel paths [70]. Effectively, thicker membranes result in a lower performance [71]. However, thinner membranes degrade faster, permeate hydrogen to the oxygen side [72] and have lower mechanical strength [58]. All these factors necessitate a trade-off between performance and durability.

The most common membrane thickness used in AEMWE is between 50–60 μm as it offers acceptable performance and durability. The effect of membrane thickness on performance has been identified to change around 100 mV for every 30 μm @ 1 A cm^{-2} , 60 °C, 1 M KOH, as shown in Fig. 7(a). The voltage required at 1 A cm^{-2} increased from 2.24 V for a 30 μm thick membrane to 2.34 V for a 60 μm and successively to 2.44 V for a 90 μm membrane.

The effect of membrane thickness at high current densities have been quantified through the ASR trends as shown in Fig. 7(b). The ASR change at 0.5 A cm^{-2} is the lowest and increases progressively between 1 to 1.4 A cm^{-2} , as shown in Fig. 7(c). The largest change in ASR is about 12% between 30 μm to 90 μm membrane thickness at 1.4 A cm^{-2} . Similar increases are observed between 30–60 μm and 60–90 μm membrane thicknesses. Although the overall ASR reduces with increasing current density (Fig. 7(b)), the change in ASR at higher current densities has a higher influence on the performance (Fig. 7(c)).

Fig. 6. The effect of temperature on the MEA observed in (a) cell performance polarization plots at 1 atm, 60 °C with 1 M KOH (pH 14), 1.56 ml min⁻¹ wet-cathode feed, (b) the different KOH concentration operating map, (c) the ASR trend for pH14 at 1 A cm⁻², (d) the ASR trend comparisons from pH12 (0.03 A cm⁻²), pH13 (0.29 A cm⁻²) and pH14 (1 A cm⁻²). (e) the HER and OER gas fractions at indicated current densities (outlet plane).

Since the membrane thickness only affects the ohmic overpotential linearly, a linear increase in the required voltage is observed as a function of membrane thickness (Fig. 7(a)). Moreover, as the ohmic overpotential is proportional to the applied current, a higher impact of membrane thickness will be observed at higher current densities (Fig. 7(b)).

3.2.4. KOH flow rate and cathode feed type

The flowrate has a direct effect on mass transfer of the electrolysis process by evacuating the bubbles generated clearing the ECSA. The two phase behaviour in the PTL and bubble formation, growth and detachment is a slow process. As bubbles start forming at higher current densities the effect of fluid flow parameters such as electrolyte flow rate become prominent. Flowrate is also a keen *design criterion* for larger

scale stacks. As the electrolysis operation is exothermic high flowrates assist in thermal management of stacks, removing excess heat.

For a wet-cathode feed (WCF) where the KOH electrolyte is introduced from both the cathode and the anode PTL, increasing the KOH electrolyte flow rate from 1 ml min⁻¹ to 2 ml min⁻¹ slightly increased the cell performance, as shown in Fig. 8(a). Although an increase in the KOH flow (f_{KOH}) rate results in a better performance between 1 to 1.56 ml min⁻¹, a further increase between 1.56 to 2 ml min⁻¹ has a lower impact. The MEA performance tends to plateau after 2 ml min⁻¹ cm⁻² due to sufficient reactant concentration at the electrodes and effective bubble evacuation [73]. In the dry cathode feed configuration (DCF), flowrates closer to 2 ml min⁻¹ cm⁻² would be necessary, as water diffusion through the membrane to the cathode could result in local reactant starvation at the anode. Higher flowrates could also result in catalyst leaching, especially in the (DCF) configuration [54,74].

Fig. 7. (a) The effect of membrane thickness on cell performance observed in polarization plots at 1 M KOH, 60 °C, 1 atm and wet-cathode feed. The model was simulated for 30 μm, 60 μm and 90 μm. (b) The cell voltage and the ASR trends for changing membrane thickness as a function of current density. (c) The increase in ASR between 30 to 60 μm (grey), 60 to 90 μm (red) and 30 to 90 μm (blue) as a function of current density.

The volume fractions at the end of the current sweep (1.41 A cm⁻²) for $f_{\text{KOH}} = 1, 1.56, 2 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$ show that high flowrates evacuate the produced gases rapidly, reducing the gas fractions, represented in Fig. 8(b). A higher KOH flow rate increases bubble interfacial area, which results in bubble detachment at a smaller size, resulting in a higher electrode–electrolyte contact surface [74]. Additionally, increasing electrolyte flow rate results in higher gas production rate, which reduces the amount of accumulated bubbles at the electrode surface [54,66,74]. The simulation of gas fractions between wet and dry cathode configurations is provided in appendix A1.

To reduce the cost of hydrogen purification downstream of the electrolysis process DCF configuration is gaining prominence. The supporting electrolyte is fed only at the anode. The diffusion of water through the membrane brings the necessary fuel for HER. In this configuration the hydrogen is drier and the gas fractions are higher. The model predicts minor performance changes due to dry cathode configuration. Although there seems to be no effect on the MEA performance, DCF could enhance degradation during stability tests [7,75,76]. As the scope of this article is to validate the developed MEA electrochemical performance model the durability studies would be considered in future work. Overall, flowrate largely effects the fluid properties while enhancing electrochemical performance.

3.3. MEA performance ranking table

As a result of the sensitivity analysis factors such as KOH concentration, temperature, membrane thickness, electrolyte feed type and flowrate can be ranked based on the effect on performance. The area-specific resistance broadly summarizes the effect of various sensitivity

parameters. In Table 5, it can be clearly seen that the KOH electrolyte concentration has the highest impact on cell performance, followed by temperature, membrane thickness, cathode feed type and KOH flow rate.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ Ni fibre – Raney[®] Ni || X37-50RT || NiFe₂O₄ – SS316L fibre AEMWE MEA is simulated using a COMSOL[®] 6.0 model. The membrane used is 60 μm thick with anode PTL (aPTL) and cathode PTL (cPTL) are 370 μm thick each, with 0.7 average porosity. The MEA simulation is initialized using the *Fuel Cell and Electrolyzers module* with hydroxide (OH⁻) exchange water electrolyzer physics in a stationary study to model the electrochemical behaviour that follows the Butler–Volmer equation. Bubble formation and two-phase effects are studied using the *CFD module* by coupling the hydroxide (OH⁻) exchange water electrolyzer physics with the Euler–Euler model, laminar flow physics interface in a time-dependent study.

A sensitivity analysis is then performed by repeating the simulation for individually tuned parameters. The main parameters studied and shown in this study are:

- KOH concentration; pH12-14, (0.01 M, 0.1 M and 1 M KOH)
- Temperature (30 °C, 50 °C, 60 °C and 80 °C)
- Membrane thickness (30 μm, 60 μm and 90 μm)
- KOH flow rate (1 ml min⁻¹, 1.56 ml min⁻¹ and 2 ml min⁻¹)
- KOH feed type (wet-cathode and dry-cathode feed)

The simulated cell is validated by three experimental tests. A three-electrode setup consisting of (working electrode) || AGAR-Ag/AgCl ||

Fig. 8. Effect of KOH flow rate and cathode feed type on cell performance as seen through: (a) polarization plot @ 60 °C, 1 M KOH, 1 atm (b) produced gas volume fractions at the end of sweep (1.41 A cm⁻²) for $f_{\text{KOH}} = 1 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$ WCF, $f_{\text{KOH}} = 1.56 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$ WCF and $f_{\text{KOH}} = 2 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$ WCF and $f_{\text{KOH}} = 1.56 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$ DCF.

Table 5
The parameter ranking table effecting the MEA performance based on ASR change.

Rank	Parameter	ASR change (%)	Contribution	Impact
1	KOH concentration <i>pH12–14, 60 °C, 2.5 V</i>	-96.97 ^a	Exchange current densities, Conductivity: Membrane, supporting electrolyte ECSA Bubble coalescence	Very high
2	Membrane thickness <i>30–90 μm, @1 A cm⁻², pH14</i>	+9.22	Membrane conductivity	High
3	Temperature <i>30–80 °C, @ 1 A cm⁻², pH14</i>	-4.34	Exchange current densities, Conductivity: Membrane, supporting electrolyte ECSA Bubble detachment	Moderate
4	Dry cathode feed <i>1.56 ml min⁻¹ cm⁻², @1 A cm⁻², pH14</i>	<0.50	Hydrogen humidity	Low
5	KOH flowrate <i>1–2 ml min⁻¹ cm⁻², @ 1 A cm⁻², pH 14</i>	>-0.50	Bubble evacuation rate and thermal management	Least

^a Negative sign indicates reduction in ASR.

Pt-wire (counter electrode) is used to validate the simulated half-cell overpotentials. Two freshly prepared MEA cells are used to validate the simulation. The first MEA validated the base case of the model (20 °C, 1 atm, 1 M KOH, with a 1.56 ml min⁻¹ total flow rate in a wet-cathode feed, introduced equally into the anode and cathode PTL from the bottom), while the second MEA was used to validate sensitivity parameters. The observations made from this study are as follows:

- For the base case, the 1 A cm⁻² current density is reached at 2.22 V for the experimental cell vs. 2.21 V for the modelled cell (<0.5% error).
- Increasing KOH concentration from 0.01 M to 1 M (pH 12 to 14), at 60 °C, increased the current density from 0.063 to 1.41 A cm⁻², 2.5 V. The current densities of 0.03, 0.29 and 1 A cm⁻² are chosen

for pH 12, 13 and 14 respectively to analyse the gas fractions. The maximum H₂ volume fractions increased from 0.3% to 7.38%.

- Increasing temperature from 30 °C to 80 °C decreased the cell voltage from 2.48 V to 2.33 V at 1 A cm⁻² at pH 14. The bubble diffusion homogenized in the PTL away from the catalyst surface with increasing temperature.
- Increasing membrane thickness from 30 to 90 μm increased the cell voltage from 2.24 to 2.44 V at 1 A cm⁻², 60 °C and 1 M KOH. The largest increase in ASR (12%) is observed between 30 μm to 90 μm membrane thickness at 1.4 A cm⁻².
- Changing the cathode feed type and increasing the KOH flow rate results in minor contributions to the polarization performance (<3 mV at 1.41 A cm⁻²). However, the contribution to the

bubble generation, growth and evacuation would affect the MEA performance a large scale stack.

- From the sensitivity analysis, the most influential parameters based on the cell's ASR change are as follows: KOH concentration (−97%), membrane thickness (+9%), temperature (−4%), cathode feed type (<+0.5%) and KOH flow rate (>−0.5%).

4.1. Future work

To move to higher green hydrogen production through AEMWE, the $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ MEA cell area needs to be scaled up ($10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$), then increased to 5-cell stack level (current lab capabilities with >1 kW). At this scale, flow field optimization, stack simulation and MEA degradation analysis for long term performance could be done to identify degradation causing parameters.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Khaled Lawand: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Suhas Nuggehalli Sampathkumar:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Zoé Mury:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Software. **Jan Van Herle:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Project administration, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve spelling, grammar and language clarity. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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